

Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of 5-Substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones and related Compounds

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THE compounds containing oxadiazole ring possess various biological activities¹. Many 3,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones are known as bacteriostatic² and many benzidine derivatives possess antimicrobial³ activity. Keeping all these in view, nineteen new 3-arylaminomethyl-5-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (1), *N,N'*-bis(3-*p*-hydroxybenzylidino-5-aryloxymethyl/aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione)benzidines (2) and *N,N'*-bis(3-methylene-5-aryloxymethyl/aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione)piperazines (3) have been prepared by the action of aldehydes and amines on oxadiazole (Scheme 1). The compounds were screened for fungicidal activity against *A. flavus*, *C. sacchari* and *H. oryzae*.

Scheme 1. Reagent : (i) HCHO, R'NH₂, (ii) *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, benzidine, (iii) HCHO, piperazine.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in an open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer. The completion of the reaction and purity of the compounds were checked by tlc in benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 3) mixtures on silica gel. The required oxadiazoles were prepared by the standard method⁴.

3-(2',4'-Dichlorophenylaminomethyl)-5-phenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (1a) : To 5-phenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (2.08 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in a minimum amount of methanol and kept in an ice-bath, was added formaldehyde (0.3 g, 0.01 mol). 2,4-Dichloroaniline (1.62 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in minimum quantity of methanol, was then added slowly to the ice-cold mixture. The resulting mixture was swirled gently and allowed to stand in an ice-bath for 3 h. The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (3.5 g, 78.5%), m.p. 125° (Found : N, 11.12 ; S, 8.19. C₁₆H₁₈Cl₂N₃O₂S requires : N, 10.99 ; S, 8.38%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 430 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 240, 1 020 (C-O-C=), 1 080 (C=S) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.3 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 3.5-3.7 (2H, d, N-CH₂-N), 6.9-7.8 (8H, m, ArH) and 9.1-9.3 (1H, b, NH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

***N,N'*-Bis(3-*p*-hydroxybenzylideno-5-*p*-chlorophenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione)benzidine (2a)** : To 5-*p*-chlorophenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (2.42 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in a minimum amount of methanol and cooled in an ice-bath, was added *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) followed by a cold methanolic solution of benzidine (0.92 g, 0.005 mol) (added dropwise with stirring). The resulting mixture was kept in an ice-bath for 3 h and the resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (4.0 g, 91.3%), m.p. 180° (Found : N, 9.38 ; S, 7.25. C₂₄H₂₄Cl₂N₆O₆S₂ requires : N, 9.58 ; S, 7.29%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 (NH), 1 610 (C=N), 1 210, 1 020 (C-O-C=), 1 160 (C=S), 820 (*p*-substitution) and 680 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.4 (4H, s, OCH₂), 3.6-4.0 (2H, d, N-CH₂-N), 4.6-4.9 (2H, b, OH), 6.7-8.1 (24H, m, ArH) and 8.6-8.9 (2H, b, NH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 2).

***N,N'*-Bis(3-methylene-5-*p*-chlorophenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione)piperazine (3a)** : To 5-*p*-chlorophenoxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (2.42 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in a minimum amount of methanol and cooled in an ice-bath, was added formaldehyde (0.3 g, 0.01 mol) followed by a cold methanolic solution of piperazine (0.43 g, 0.005 mol) added dropwise with stirring. The resulting mixture was left in an ice-bath for 3 h. The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (2.32 g, 78.1%), m.p. 140° (Found : N, 14.04 ; S, 10.66. C₂₄H₂₄Cl₂N₆O₄S₂ requires : N, 14.12 ; S, 10.75%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 610 (C=N), 1 240, 1 010 (C-O-C), 1 160 (C=S) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) ; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.4 (4H, s, OCH₂), 4.0-4.5 (12H, m, -NCH₂) and 6.9-8.4 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 2).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Compd. no.	R	R'	Yield %	M p. °C	Mol. formula
1a	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	78	125	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1b	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ N	64	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
1c	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₃	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	88	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
1d	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	61	110	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1e	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	70	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
1f	3-CH ₃ -4 Cl.C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	65	120	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1g	3-CH ₃ -4-Cl.C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2-C ₆ H ₄ N	83	178	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
1h	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	58	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
1i	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₃	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	76	110	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ S
1j	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	68	148	C ₆ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS
1k	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2-C ₆ H ₄ N	94	194	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS
1l	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	92	121	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS
1m	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2-C ₁₀ H ₇	86	112	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS

*All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses for N and S.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3*

Compd. no	R	Yield %	M p. °C	Mol. formula
2a	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	91	180	C ₄₄ H ₃₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂
2b	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	72	215	C ₄₆ H ₄₀ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂
2c	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	82	190	C ₄₄ H ₃₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3a	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	78	140	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3b	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	65	102	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3c	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	81	186	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂

*All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses for N and S.

Fungicidal screening: All compounds were screened for their fungicidal activity by agar-growth technique⁵ against *A. flavus*, *C. sacchari* and *H. oryzae* at three different concentrations, viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm.

The results obtained at concentration of 10 ppm after 96 h showed that all the compounds display fairly good level of fungicidal activity against all three fungi but are slightly less active against *C. sacchari* than against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae*. The piperazines/benzidines are less fungicidal than the corresponding mono-Mannich bases. The introduction of a benzidine moiety in place of a piperazine and a *p*-hydroxybenzylidene group in a place of methyleno group does not show any marked effect on the fungicidal activity. In general, the compounds having chlorophenoxy or *p*-chloro-*m*-methyl phenoxy moiety at position-5 are more fungicidal.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some Bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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MANY 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles possess various biological activities¹. Acid hydrazides and their condensed products are also associated with biological activities^{2, 3}. All these facts led us to undertake the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of the titled compounds.

The dihydrazide of malonic acid⁴, various substituted malonanilic acid hydrazides² and bis-(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)methane⁵ (1) were